

HyDelta 3

WP5d – Permeation in the gas distribution grid

WP5d.1 – Impact on safety due to permeation in gas distribution grids

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- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
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- Conversion (of the distribution network)
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- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

Safety in the management and operation of the gas distribution network is a top priority for Dutch gas distribution network operators to minimize risks to people and the environment. Extensive research is therefore being conducted on various topics regarding safety for the future distribution of hydrogen. This research includes examining the effects of hydrogen and oxygen permeation on the gas composition in gas distribution pipelines, gas pressure reduction and regulation stations, and casing pipes. Permeation is a natural and unavoidable process. Due to the higher concentration of oxygen outside the pipeline, oxygen from the surrounding environment will permeate through the pipe wall into the gas network. Conversely, hydrogen from the gas network can permeate through the pipe wall to the environment. As a result, a hydrogen-oxygen mixture may form at various locations in the distribution network.

Permeation reduces gas quality, which can be detrimental to users and combustion appliances¹. Additionally, permeation may lead to the formation of a flammable mixture, potentially impacting safety during normal operations or maintenance work on the network. However, how the hydrogen-oxygen ratio evolves over time and in which situations a flammable mixture may form is not yet well understood.

Using a combination of research data and literature-based permeability coefficients and rates, Kiwa has modeled the evolution of the hydrogen-to-oxygen ratio due to permeation for selected scenarios, in consultation with a supervisory group. An essential condition for these calculations is that no gas exchange (no flow or diffusion) occurs within the pipeline. The models indicate that in certain situations, a flammable mixture may form inside a pipeline, technical installation of a gas pressure reduction and regulation station, or casing pipe (see Table 1). However, a flammable mixture in a pipeline does not pose a danger if an ignition source is missing. One potential ignition source that has been considered is static electricity caused by dust transport within the piping system. The presence of an ignition source due to static electricity can be ruled out in all cases where a flammable hydrogen-oxygen mixture could be present according to this research. This is because in the absence of gas flow static charge from dust transport cannot build up. When the gas flow resumes, the pipeline length, the amount of dust present, and the duration of dust transport are insufficient to generate a static charge capable of producing a spark with enough ignition energy. In HyDelta 4, follow-up research is being conducted to the buildup of static charge in the distribution network. In situations where a flammable mixture may be present in the pipeline due to permeation, and maintenance work is carried out on a hydrogen network in pilot projects, it is concluded that the implementation of the appropriate precautionary measures is sufficient to mitigate risks. Potential safety risks can be mitigated by including them in work instructions, flushing pipelines before performing maintenance, and using appropriate indoor combustion appliances. Additionally, practical tests can further improve insights into the possible formation of a flammable mixture in various scenarios.

¹ In HyDelta3 WP1a research has been carried out on the influence of permeation on gas quality.

Table 1: Overview of the situations where permeation does and does not cause safety risks.

No.	Situation	Realistic scenario	Conclusion theoretical approach
1	Main line closed off by temporary sealing methods	No	The theory shows that a flammable mixture can form in a PE mainline within 118 days. For a PVC mainline, this takes 155 days. This is not a realistic situation, as a blockage with temporary sealing measures is maintained for only a few hours to a few days. In this case, permeation does not pose a potential safety risk.
2	Main line blocked in	No	The theory shows that a flammable mixture can form in a PE mainline within 118 days. For a PVC mainline, this takes 155 days. This is not a realistic situation, as the blocking of a main pipeline is maintained for only a few days. In this case, permeation does not pose a potential safety risk.
3	Main line in casing pipes	Yes	If the casing pipe of a mainline is completely sealed gas-tight, calculations show that a flammable mixture can form within 0.15 to 12 days in a PE casing pipe. For PVC, this takes 1.7 to 7.6 days. It is likely that at least a small volume of flammable mixture may be present in the middle of the casing pipe. Therefore it is advised to take additional safety measures during (maintenance) activities, such as checking the gas concentration before starting the activities.
4	Main line permeates to environment	No	The hydrogen will disperse through the soil and escape into the environment. In all scenarios, the hydrogen concentration remains well below the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air. Therefore, the permeation of hydrogen through mainlines into the environment will not pose a safety risk for the scenarios based on the assumptions of this study.
5	Saddle on main line to the main tap before meter installation	Yes	If the hydrogen gas in a PE service line remains stationary and is completely closed off from the rest of the network for an extended period of time, calculations show that a flammable mixture can form within 17.4 days. This period without flow is considered realistic. Therefore, it is advised to take additional safety measures during (maintenance) activities and to be mindful of this when restarting appliances. Potential safety risks during maintenance can be addressed by identifying the risks in work instructions. Additionally, it may be considered to first purge the pipeline and flare off the gas using a (mini) flare with a flame arrestor. Preventive flushing before starting activities is also an option.
6	Service line in casing pipe	No	In the scenario where a PE casing pipe around a PE service line is completely sealed (non-ventilated), a flammable mixture can form within 3 hours to 17 days, depending on the selected dimensions and pressure. However, standard wall-penetrating casing pipes are generally sufficiently open, preventing the accumulation of hydrogen. Therefore, in this situation, is not regarded as realistic and permeation does not pose a safety risk [1].
7	Service line permeates to environment (Saddle on	No	The hydrogen will disperse through the soil and escape into the environment. In all scenarios, the hydrogen concentration remains well below the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air. Therefore, the permeation

	main line to the main valve before meter installation)		of hydrogen through service lines into the environment will not pose a safety risk for the scenarios based on the assumptions of this study.
8	Technical installation station blocked between isolation valves	Yes	<p>In the situation where a HAS or AS is blocked on one side to disconnect a customer while keeping the station pressurized, enough time can pass for a flammable mixture to form in the pipelines: 70 days for HAS and 109 days for AS. Therefore, it is advised to take additional safety measures during (maintenance) activities. Potential safety risks during (maintenance) activities on stations can be addressed by identifying them in the work instructions. Additionally, it may be considered to flare off the gas contents using a (mini) flare with a flame arrestor before starting any activities.</p> <p>For DS, this blocking is only done intentionally for maintenance work. During maintenance, the blocked sections are put back into operation within a day. Within 24 hours, permeation cannot create a flammable mixture in the installation for both single-stream and double-stream DS. In this case, permeation does not pose a potential safety risk.</p>
9	Technical installation station blocked between inlet (and outlet) valve	Yes	<p>For maintenance on the technical installation of a station, the installation is sometimes blocked between the inlet and outlet shut-off valves. This short closure, lasting a maximum of a few hours, is not sufficient to create a flammable mixture in the pipeline. In worst-case scenarios, 5.4 days are required for HAS, 6.4 days for AS, and 82 days for DS. Potential safety risks during maintenance activities on stations can be addressed by identifying them in the work instructions. Opening the safety valve in this situation will allow flow and expel any mixture from the installation.</p> <p>However, if a safety valve fails, it is possible for a HAS or DS installation to be blocked on one side. Over time, until the next maintenance cycle, permeation could lead to the formation of a flammable mixture in the installation. Therefore, it is advised to take additional safety measures during (maintenance) activities.</p>
10	The in-active control line of a dual-line installation of gas pressure and regulation station	Yes	<p>The inactive control line of a dual-line installation in an AS or DS may remain unused for an extended period (months), assuming that the gas does not mix with the main network.</p> <p>If we disregard the mixing of hydrogen and oxygen in the reserve line with the outgoing network, there is a possibility that a flammable mixture could form after 6.4 days (AS) and 82 days (DS) and still be present when (maintenance) activities are carried out. Therefore, it is advised to take additional safety measures during (maintenance) activities. Potential safety risks during station maintenance can be addressed by identifying them in the work instructions. Additionally, it may be considered to flare off the pipeline contents using a (mini) flare with a flame arrestor before starting any activities.</p>

Samenvatting

Veiligheid in beheer en gebruik van het gasdistributienet staat voorop bij de Nederlandse gasdistributienetbeheerders om risico's voor mens en milieu te minimaliseren. Voor de toekomstige distributie van waterstof wordt daarom ook uitgebreid onderzoek gedaan naar veiligheid. Daarbij is onder andere aandacht voor het effect van permeatie van waterstof en zuurstof op de gassamenstelling in gasdistributieleidingen, gasstations, en mantelbuizen. Permeatie is een natuurlijk en onvermijdelijk proces. Als gevolg van de hogere concentratie zuurstof buiten de leiding, zal zuurstof vanuit de omgeving door de buiswand heen het gasnet in permeëren. Omgekeerd kan waterstof vanuit het gasnet door de buiswand heen naar buiten permeëren. Daardoor kan er op verschillende locaties van het distributienet een waterstof-zuurstofmengsel ontstaan.

Door permeatie neemt de gaskwaliteit af, wat nadelig kan zijn voor gebruikers en verbrandingsapparaten². Daarnaast bestaat de kans dat door permeatie een brandbaar mengsel ontstaat wat mogelijk gevolgen heeft voor de veiligheid bij reguliere bedrijfsvoering of werkzaamheden aan het net. Hoe de verhouding waterstof-zuurstof zich over tijd ontwikkelt, en in welke situaties kans is op het ontstaan van een brandbaar mengsel is onvoldoende bekend. Daarnaast is niet duidelijk wat de kans op ontsteking ten gevolge van staticiteit in de leiding of door werkzaamheden is.

Kiwa heeft door een combinatie van uit onderzoek en literatuur bekende permeatiecoëfficiënten en -snelheden voor de, in overleg met de begeleidingsgroep gekozen, situaties het verloop van de verhouding waterstof : zuurstof door permeatie gemodelleerd. Een essentiële randvoorwaarde om de berekening mogelijk te maken, is dat er geen uitwisseling van gassen (geen stroming en diffusie) in de leiding plaatsvindt. Uit de modellen volgt dat er verschillende situaties zijn waarbij door permeatie een brandbaar mengsel kan ontstaan in een leiding, technische installatie van een gasstation of mantelbuis (zie tabel 2). Een brandbaar mengsel in een leiding vormt echter geen gevaar wanneer een ontstekingsbron mist. Een ontstekingsbron waarnaar gekeken kan worden is staticiteit als gevolg van stoftransport. De aanwezigheid van een ontstekingsbron ten gevolge van staticiteit kan in alle gevallen waar een brandbaar waterstof-zuurstofmengsel zich bevindt, uitgesloten worden. Door de afwezigheid van stroming kan statische lading als gevolg van stoftransport namelijk niet worden opgebouwd. Wanneer de gasstroom weer op gang komt, is de lengte van de leiding, de hoeveelheid aanwezige stof, of de tijd met stoftransport onvoldoende om tot een statische lading te komen waarbij een vonk zou kunnen ontstaan met genoeg ontstekingsenergie. In HyDelta 4 wordt er vervolgonderzoek uitgevoerd naar de opbouw van statische lading in het distributienet. In die situaties waarbij door permeatie een brandbaar mengsel in de leiding aanwezig kan zijn, en werkzaamheden aan een waterstofnet bij pilotprojecten plaatsvinden, wordt geconcludeerd dat de inzet van de juiste voorzorgsmaatregelen voldoende om veiligheid te borgen. De mogelijke veiligheidsrisico's kunnen worden gemitigeerd door deze te benoemen in de werkinstructies, door te spoelen voor het uitvoeren van werkzaamheden, en door gebruik maken van geschikte verbrandingstoestellen binnenshuis. Daarnaast kunnen praktijktesten nog beter inzicht geven in de kans op vorming van brandbare mengsels in de verschillende situaties.

² In Hydelta3 WP1a is onderzoek gedaan naar de gevolgen van permeatie op de gaskwaliteit.

Tabel 2: Overzicht van situaties waarbij permeatie al dan niet een potentieel veiligheidsrisico vormt.

Nr.	Situatie	Realistisch scenario	Conclusie theoretische benadering
1	Hoofdleiding afgesloten door tijdelijke afsluitmiddelen	Nee	Uit de theorie blijkt dat er in 118 dagen in een PE-hoofdleiding een brandbaar mengsel kan ontstaan. Voor een PVC-hoofdleiding is dit 155 dagen. Dit is geen realistische situatie, omdat de afsluiting met tijdelijke afsluitmiddelen slechts enkele dagen wordt gehandhaafd. In dit geval vormt permeatie geen potentieel veiligheidsrisico.
2	Hoofdleiding ingeblokt	Nee	Uit de theorie blijkt dat er in 118 dagen in een PE-hoofdleiding een brandbaar mengsel kan ontstaan. Voor een PVC-hoofdleiding is dit 155 dagen. Dit is geen realistische situatie, omdat het inblokken van een hoofdleiding slechts enkele dagen wordt gehandhaafd. In dit geval vormt permeatie geen potentieel veiligheidsrisico.
3	Hoofdleiding in mantelbuis	Ja	Als een mantelbuis van een hoofdleiding volledig gasdicht is afgesloten, kan zich volgens de berekeningen binnen 0,15 – 12 dagen een brandbaar mengsel in een PE-mantelbuis vormen. Voor PVC is dit 1,7-7,6 dagen. Het is zeer aannemelijk dat op zijn minst in het midden van de mantelbuis een klein volume brandbaar mengsel aanwezig kan zijn. Het is aan te raden om bij werkzaamheden extra veiligheidsmaatregelen te treffen. Hierbij kan bijvoorbeeld worden gedacht aan het controleren van de gasconcentratie voorafgaand aan de werkzaamheden.
4	Hoofdleiding permeëert naar omgeving	Nee	Het waterstof zal verspreiden door de bodem en ontsnappen naar de omgeving. De concentratie waterstof ligt in alle scenario's ruim onder de onderste brandbaarheids grens van waterstof in lucht. Permeatie van waterstof door hoofdleidingen naar de omgeving zal voor de scenario's met aannames van deze studie daarom geen veiligheidsrisico vormen.
5	Aftakzadel tot kraan voor de gasmeter	Ja	Wanneer het gas in een PE-aansluitleiding stilstaat en voor langere tijd volledig is afgesloten van de rest van het net, kan volgens de berekeningen in 17,4 dagen een brandbaar mengsel ontstaan. Deze periode van stilstand wordt als realistisch ingeschat. Het is daarom aan te raden om bij werkzaamheden extra veiligheidsmaatregelen te treffen en hier bedacht op te zijn bij het opstarten van toestellen. Mogelijke veiligheidsrisico's tijdens werkzaamheden aan de leiding kunnen worden geadresseerd door de risico's te benoemen in de werkinstructies. Daarnaast kan worden overwogen om de leiding eerst gasloos te maken en affakkelen met (mini)fakkel met vlamdover. Ook preventief spoelen voor werkzaamheden is hier een optie.
6	Aansluitleiding in mantelbuis	Nee	In het scenario waar een PE-mantelbuis om een PE-aansluitleiding volledig gasdicht afgesloten (niet-geventileerd) is, kan binnen 3 uur tot 17 dagen (afhankelijk van de gekozen dimensies en druk) een

			<p>brandbaar mengsel ontstaan. Gewone geveldoorvoerende mantelbuizen zijn in beginsel echter voldoende open, waardoor er geen accumulatie van waterstof kan plaatsvinden. In deze situatie vormt permeatie daarom geen veiligheidsrisico [1].</p>
7	Aansluitleiding permeëert naar omgeving (aftakzadel tot hoofdkraan voor de gasmeter)	Nee	<p>Het waterstof zal verspreiden door de bodem en ontsnappen naar de omgeving. De concentratie waterstof ligt in alle scenario's ruim onder de onderste brandbaarheidsgrens van waterstof in lucht. Permeatie van waterstof door aansluitleidingen naar de omgeving zal voor de scenario's met aannames van deze studie daarom geen veiligheidsrisico vormen.</p>
8	Gasstation ingeblokt tussen scheidingsafsluiter(s)	Ja	<p>In de situatie waarbij een HAS of AS eenzijdig wordt ingeblokt om een klant af te sluiten en er wordt gekozen om het station op druk te houden, kan voldoende tijd verstrijken om een brandbaar mengsel in de leidingen te laten ontstaan: 70 dagen voor HAS, 109 dagen voor AS. Het is daarom aan te raden om bij werkzaamheden extra veiligheidsmaatregelen te treffen. Mogelijke veiligheidsrisico's tijdens werkzaamheden aan gasstations kunnen worden geadresseerd door de risico's te benoemen in de werkinstructies. Daarnaast kan worden overwogen om voor de aanvang van werkzaamheden de inhoud van de leiding af te fakkelen met (mini)fakkelt met vlamdoover.</p> <p>Voor DS geldt dat dit inblokken alleen voor onderhoudswerkzaamheden bewust wordt gedaan. Bij onderhoudswerkzaamheden zijn de afgesloten delen binnen een dag weer in bedrijf. Binnen 24 uur kan er in deze sectie bij een enkelstraats en dubbelstraats DS door permeatie ook geen brandbaar mengsel in de installatie ontstaan. In dit geval vormt permeatie geen potentieel veiligheidsrisico.</p>
9	Technische installatie ingeblokt tussen de inlaatafsluiter (en uitlaatafsluiter)	Ja	<p>Voor werkzaamheden aan de technische installatie van een gasstation, wordt de technische installatie ook wel ingeblokt tussen de in- en uitlaat afsluiters van de installatie. Deze korte afsluiting van max. enkele uren is niet voldoende om een brandbaar mengsel in de leiding te creëren. Daarvoor moeten 5,4 dagen voor HAS, 6,4 dagen voor AS en 82 dagen voor DS verstrijken voor de worst case scenario's. Mogelijke veiligheidsrisico's tijdens werkzaamheden aan gasstations kunnen worden geadresseerd door de risico's te benoemen in de werkinstructies. Het opentrekken van de veiligheid zal in deze situatie voor doorstroming zorgen en het mengsel uit de installatie verdrijven.</p> <p>Door het vallen van een veiligheid is het wel mogelijk dat de installatie van een HAS of DS eenzijdig wordt afgeblokt. In de tijd die verstrijkt tot een volgende onderhoudsbeurt kan door permeatie bij DS en HAS een brandbaar mengsel in de installatie ontstaan. Het is daarom aan te raden om bij werkzaamheden extra veiligheidsmaatregelen te treffen.</p>

10	Enkele regelstraat (Reserve regelstraat van dubbele regelstraat)	Ja	De niet-actieve regelstraat van een dubbelstraats-installatie van een AS of DS kan gedurende langere tijd (maanden) niet wordt gebruikt en aangenomen dat het gas niet kan vermengen met het achterliggende net. Wanneer we vermenging van waterstof en zuurstof in de reserve straat met de rest van het uitgaande net buiten beschouwing laten, bestaat de kans dat na 6,4 dagen (AS) en 82 dagen (DS) een brandbaar mengsel ontstaat en aanwezig is als vervolgens werkzaamheden worden uitgevoerd. Het is daarom aan te raden om bij werkzaamheden extra veiligheidsmaatregelen te treffen. Mogelijke veiligheidsrisico's tijdens werkzaamheden aan gasstations kunnen worden geadresseerd door de risico's te benoemen in de werkinstructies. Daarnaast kan worden overwogen om voor de aanvang van werkzaamheden de inhoud van de leiding af te fakkelen met (mini)fakkel met vlamdover.
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1. In some situations there is a possibility that permeation can lead to flammable mixtures in a gas pipeline, casing pipe or station

Permeation is a natural and unavoidable process in which a permeate (a gas, vapor or liquid) moves through a physical barrier layer, such as a pipeline wall. The permeation process is driven by a difference in concentration of the permeate. In the case of gas pipelines, this is the difference between the gas concentrations on either side of the pipe wall. As a result of the higher concentration of hydrogen inside the pipe, hydrogen will permeate from inside the gas network to the outside. Conversely, oxygen (one of the main components of air, 21%) can also permeate from the atmosphere into the gas network. A hydrogen-oxygen mixture can be created by permeation at various locations: in a gas pipeline or technical installation of a station, in a (closed) casing pipe, or in the environment. In this study, an estimate has been given of the time that must elapse before a flammable mixture can be created by permeation for various situations for the assets: main lines (1.1), service lines (1.2) and stations (1.3). The possible presence of a flammable mixture can affect the execution of maintenance activities. In order to be able to make these estimates, assumptions have been made that cause the situations considered to deviate from reality. A short description of the boundary conditions is given below for the various locations where the mixture can occur. A complete overview of the boundary conditions and assumptions can be found in “Appendix I – Methods and boundary conditions”. For a more accurate estimate, CFD calculations or practical measurements will have to be performed.

Flammable mixture in a gas pipeline or technical installation of a stations:

For the formation of a flammable mixture in a gas pipeline or technical installation of a station, it is assumed that the hydrogen gas is stationary and not in contact with other parts of the gas network. At the same time, oxygen permeates into the pipeline and hydrogen permeates out of the pipeline via the pipe wall in the case of a gas pipeline and via the rubber parts in the case of a gas pressure reduction and regulation station. After a certain time, the percentage of oxygen has increased to such an extent and the percentage of hydrogen has decreased to such an extent that the upper flammability limit³ is reached (see Appendix I for a detailed explanation of the selected flammability limits). It is then determined whether this scenario, which is the combination of the selected section plus the period of standstill, can occur in reality. If this is the case, permeation may pose a safety risk during (maintenance) activities and, when considering service lines, for starting up appliances. The most critical situation for the formation of a flammable mixture in the gas pipeline or technical installation is the situation in which the upper flammability limit is reached the fastest. This means that the volume of hydrogen in the pipe is the smallest (a combination of smallest DN and lowest operating pressure), and that the permeation rate (Q) is as large as possible (the barrier layer, the wall thickness (e), is as thin as possible). In this situation, the volumes of flammable mixture are also the smallest, and thus the effects of ignition are also limited. The least critical situation has also been calculated to provide a time range in which a flammable mixture can develop. The volumes of flammable mixture in the situations can differ, and therefore the possible effects of ignition as well. The effects of ignition of different volumes are not discussed in this report. In order to gain more insight into this, the effects will have to be studied in further research.

³Upper flammability limit = 95.2% H₂. For comparison, for methane (the main component of natural gas) this is: 15.0% CH₄

Flammable mixture in a casing pipe:

For the formation of a flammable mixture in a casing pipe, the calculation assumes that the casing pipe is not ventilated. The oxygen that is present between the casing pipe and the gas line can permeate into the gas line, but is not replenished by permeation from the environment through the casing pipe wall or end seals. The amount of oxygen present in the casing pipe therefore decreases. Conversely, hydrogen can permeate from the gas line into the casing pipe and accumulate there. After a certain time, the percentage of hydrogen has increased to such an extent and the percentage of oxygen has decreased to such an extent that the lower flammability limit⁴ is reached. It is then determined whether this situation can occur in reality. If so, permeation may pose a safety risk during (maintenance) activities. The most critical situation for the formation of a flammable mixture in the casing pipe is the situation in which the lower flammability limit is reached most quickly. For the most critical situation, the volume between the gas line and the casing pipe must be as small as possible, and the permeation rate (Q) of the hydrogen from the gas line must be as large as possible (the wall thickness (e) must be as small as possible, the operating pressure in the gas line must be as high as possible). In this situation, the volumes of the flammable mixture are also the smallest, and thus the possible effects of ignition are also smallest. The least critical situation is the one in which the volume between the gas line and the casing pipe is the largest and the operating pressure is the lowest. The volumes of the flammable mixture in the situations can differ, and therefore the possible effects of ignition. The effects of ignition of different volumes are not discussed in this report. In order to gain more insight into this, the effects will have to be studied in further research.

Flammable mixture in the vicinity:

It is assumed that the pipe in which the flammable mixture forms is completely surrounded by air on the outside. This means that the soil is well ventilated, effects of soil inhomogeneity, capillary water present, cracks, another non-gas-permeable layer, and the like are excluded. The hydrogen concentration in the environment was estimated by comparing the permeation rate (ml/h) with the leak rate (ml/h) from [2] and the observed concentration of hydrogen at ground level directly above the pipe. In [2] a concentration of 5% hydrogen was detected with a soil probe for a leak of 120.2 l/h (120,200 ml/h) of hydrogen. For a gas line section with a permeation rate of 1.2 ml/h, the concentration corresponds to 0.000050% ($5.0 \cdot 10^{-5}\%$). It is then determined whether this situation, the concentration present, may pose a safety risk during (maintenance) activities (i.e. whether it exceeds the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air). The most critical situation for the formation of a flammable mixture in the environment is when the lower flammability limit is reached most quickly. This means that the permeation rate (Q) is as high as possible, which is a combination of largest DN, highest operating pressure and smallest wall thickness (e).

In the paragraphs below, the different sections and selected most and least critical situations per asset group are described. All other possible situations with other DN, pressure and wall thickness lie in the range between these two. In “ Appendix III – Calculated situations” the outcome of several additional situations have been added.

⁴Lower flammability limit: 4.0% H₂. For comparison, for methane (the main component of natural gas) this is: 5.3% CH₄.

A flammable mixture does not necessarily pose a danger when there is no ignition source

Due to permeation, it is not inconceivable that flammable mixtures are present in the gas network. This occurs in specific situations where there is no flow for a longer period of time and there is insufficient diffusion with the rest of the network.

A flammable mixture in a gas line does not necessarily pose a safety risk. For ignition of a flammable mixture, an ignition source with sufficient ignition energy is also required. An ignition source within the gas lines that can be considered is static as a result of dust transport. In order to obtain sufficient ignition energy as a result of static charging and discharge in a pipe line, the following minimum boundary conditions are required:

- There must be a quantity of dust of approximately 0.5 vol%;
- There must be a gas velocity (for hydrogen) of more than 5 m/s;
- The plastic pipe through which gas is transported must be made of PVC or PE;
- The above combination of factors must be present in the gas line for at least 10 minutes.

The presence of an ignition source due to static in a casing pipe can be ruled out. The required high velocity flow (> 5m/s) for a long(er) period (approximately 10 minutes) is absent in a casing pipe. As a result, insufficient static charge can be built up to produce a spark with sufficient ignition energy. This also applies to service lines where the gas is stationary for a longer period of time. Even if the gas flow in a service line starts up again after a long stationary period, the gas line is not long enough to build up sufficient static charge while the flammable mixture is still in the pipe. The presence of an ignition source due to static in a station can therefore be ruled out. The required high velocity flow, the amount of dust and the long(er) time with dust transport are absent in a gas pressure regulation station. Due to the very short length of steel pipes in a station, only minimal static charge can be built up during the time that a flammable mixture is present. In addition, there is a dust filter on the upstream side of the regulator, which removes any dust from the gas flow. In all cases where a flammable hydrogen-oxygen mixture can be present in the gas line through permeation, the length of the gas line, the amount of dust present, or the time with dust transport is insufficient to create a static charge that could cause a spark with sufficient ignition energy.

It is not sufficiently known what the chance is of the presence of an ignition source and thus the chance of ignition when working on hydrogen networks. Therefore, precautionary measures are recommended to ensure that engineers are aware of the possible safety risks, and that flammable mixtures are expelled before activities are carried out. In addition, it is recommended to use suitable equipment, and to conduct further research into the consequences of a flammable mixture for the operation of consumer appliances.

1.1 In 1 of the 4 situations caution is required when working on main lines

For the asset main lines, four situations have been identified for which the concentration profile of hydrogen and oxygen by permeation has been modeled. These are:

- The formation of a flammable mixture in a gas pipeline (situation [1](#) and [2](#)).
- The formation of a flammable mixture in a completely closed casing pipe (situation [3](#)).
- The formation of a flammable mixture in the environment (situation [4](#)).

There is a chance that in one of the four situations a flammable mixture will develop over time through permeation, which may still be present when (maintenance) activities are being carried out. This concerns: accumulation of hydrogen gas from a main line in a casing pipe. When working on casing pipes of main lines, extra attention is therefore required. table 3 shows the conclusions of the situations for main lines, followed by a detailed elaboration of the individual situations.

Table 3: Conclusions effect of permeation on the formation of flammable mixtures in asset main line

No.	Situation	Conclusion theoretical calculation (appendix I)
1	Main line closed by temporary flow stop equipment	The theory shows that a flammable mixture can form in a PE main line in 118 days. For a PVC main line this is 155 days. This is not a realistic situation, because the closure with temporary flow stop equipment is only maintained for a few days. In this case permeation does not pose a potential safety risk.
2	Main line blocked	The theory shows that a flammable mixture can form in a PE main line in 118 days. For a PVC main line this is 155 days. This is not a realistic situation, because the blocking of a main line is only maintained for a few days. In this case permeation does not pose a potential safety risk.
3	Main line in casing pipe	If a casing pipe of a main line is completely sealed gas-tight, a small volume of flammable mixture can form in a PE casing pipe within 0.15-12 days, according to calculations. For PVC this is 1.7-7.6 days. It is very likely that a flammable mixture can be present at least in the middle of the casing pipe. It is therefore advisable to take additional safety measures when working on these sections (see elaboration below for specific recommendations).
4	Main line permeates to environment	The hydrogen will spread through the soil and escape to the environment. The concentration of hydrogen in all scenarios is well below the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air. Permeation of hydrogen through main lines to the environment will therefore not pose a safety risk for the scenarios with assumptions of this study.

When a main line is closed by temporary flow stop equipment, no flammable mixture is formed by permeation (1)

Situation sketch and assumptions

If the gas supply has to be temporarily stopped during (maintenance) activities on a main line, temporary flow stop equipment can be used. The calculations were made for PE and PVC, the worst

case situation. An example Appendix II – Calculation example of hydrogen permeation of hydrogen permeation. This shows that hydrogen permeation through steel pipes is a factor of 10-100 smaller.

Results

In a PE main line, a flammable mixture can occur after **118 days** in the most critical situation⁵. For the least critical situation⁶ the time that must elapse before a flammable mixture has formed is up to **6390 days**. All other possible situations with other DN, pressure and wall thickness lie between these two extremes. In a PVC main line, a flammable mixture can occur after **155 days** in the most critical situation⁷. For the least critical situation⁸ the time that must elapse is up to **1950 days**. All other possible situations with other DN, operating pressure and wall thickness lie between these two extremes.

Conclusion and possible measures

Typically, activities involving temporary flow stop equipment is completed within one day. In extreme cases, a section is closed off by temporary flow stop equipment for a maximum of a few days (2-3). A scenario in which temporary flow stop equipment interrupts the gas flow for at least 118 or 155 days is therefore not realistic. Because this scenario will not occur in practice, permeation when closing of PE and PVC main lines with temporary flow stop equipment does not pose a potential safety risk for (maintenance) activities.

[In a blocked main line, no flammable mixture is formed by permeation \(2\)](#)

Situation sketch and assumptions

If the gas supply has to be temporarily stopped during activities on a main line, this can be done by blocking a section of the pipeline. It is assumed that the blocked section is completely closed off from the rest of the network. The pipeline section of this situation is the same as that of the situation above.

Results

In a PE main line, a flammable mixture can form after **118 days** in the most critical situation. For the least critical situation, this is **6390 days**. In a PVC main line, a flammable mixture can form after **155 days** in the most critical situation. For the least critical situation this is **1950 days**. All other possible situations with other DN, operating pressure and wall thickness lie between these two extremes.

Conclusion and possible measures

In practice, it will never happen that a main line is blocked for 118 or 155 days. The scenario that a flammable mixture forms in this line section with stagnant hydrogen gas is therefore not realistic. Permeation therefore does not form a potential safety risk for (maintenance) activities when blocking PE and PVC main line sections.

[In a main line in a casing pipe, a flammable mixture can form due to permeation \(3\)](#)

Situation sketch and assumptions

At underpasses (such as road or water crossings) a gas line should preferably be laid in a casing pipe. The ends of the casing pipe must be sealed with plastic covers (end seals) [3].

Results

If a casing pipe is completely sealed gas-tight, a flammable mixture can form in the casing pipe within a short period of time, according to the calculations. For a combination of PE main line and casing

⁵PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 0.1 bar

⁶PE - 250 mm - 14.8 mm - 8 bar

⁷PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar

⁸PVC - 250 mm - 6.2 mm - 0.1 bar (indicated by the guidance group that 100 mbar is the highest expected pressure in the PVC main line)

pipe, a flammable mixture can form after **0.15 days (within 4 hours)** in the most critical situation⁹. For a less critical situation¹⁰, when a larger casing pipe is used, this becomes **2.2 days**. A combination of a PVC main line and casing pipe can form after **1.9 days** in the most critical situation¹¹ a flammable mixture in the casing pipe. For a less critical situation¹² this increases to **12 days**. The volumes of flammable mixture that can form in the space between the gas line and casing pipe are small.

Conclusion and possible measures

The calculation is based on a completely gas-tight casing; hydrogen and oxygen cannot leave the space between the gas line and the casing. In reality, hydrogen and oxygen can also permeate through the casing and the end seals. Furthermore, the seals are not allowed to form a gas-tight seal¹³. The seals may contain small openings through which hydrogen can escape to the environment and oxygen can enter the casing pipe. It is not known what effect these have on the gas mixture in the casing pipe. The influence will differ per situation and depends on various factors, including but not limited to the dimensions of the casing pipe, the seals used, the location in the casing pipe in relation to the pipe ends. Additional research can provide more certainty in this regard. It is very likely that a small volume of flammable mixture may be present at least in the middle of the casing pipe. It is therefore advised to take additional safety measures when carrying out (maintenance) activities. This could include checking the gas concentration prior to carrying out (maintenance) activities.

In the event of permeation from a main line to the environment, no flammable mixture is formed by permeation (4)

Situation sketch and assumptions

By distributing hydrogen gas via the current natural gas distribution network, hydrogen gas will permeate through the pipe wall to the environment. This hydrogen will spread through the soil and escape to the environment.

Results

Even for the most critical situations, it is not possible to create a flammable mixture in the environment above main lines according to the calculation. Above a PE main line a concentration of **$1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ %** hydrogen in air can occur at ground level in the most critical situation¹⁴. For the least critical situation¹⁵ the concentration drops to **$0.17 \cdot 10^{-4}$ %**. Above a PVC main line a concentration of **$4.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ %** hydrogen in air can occur at ground level in the most critical situation¹⁶. In the least critical situation¹⁷ the concentration drops to **$3.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ %**.

Conclusion and possible measures

The concentration of hydrogen is in all situations well below the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air (4%). Permeation of hydrogen through main lines to the environment for the scenarios with assumptions of this study will therefore not pose a safety risk.

⁹(B) PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 75 mm - 4.5 mm

¹⁰(B) PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 110 mm - 6.6 mm

¹¹(B) PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 75 mm - 2 mm

¹²(B) PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 110 mm - 2.7 mm

¹³The NEN 7244-1 states that casing pipes must be sealed at both ends to prevent flushing. However, the seal must not prevent a leak from the gas-carrying pipe from being detectable.

¹⁴PE - 250 mm - 14.8 mm - 8 bar

¹⁵PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 0.1 bar

¹⁶PVC - 250mm - 6.2mm - 0.1 bar

¹⁷PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar

1.2 In 2 out of 3 situations caution is required when working on service lines

For the asset service lines, three situations have been identified for which the concentration profile of hydrogen and oxygen by permeation has been modeled. These are:

- The formation of a flammable mixture in the section of the service line from the branch saddle to the valve for the meter (situation [5](#)).
- The formation of a flammable mixture in a completely closed casing pipe (situation [6](#)).
- The formation of a flammable mixture in the environment outside the home (situation [7](#)).

There is a chance that in two of the three situations a flammable mixture will be created by permeation over time. The situation in which hydrogen accumulates in a non-ventilated casing pipe and oxygen enters a service line requires extra attention when carrying out (maintenance) activities. Table 4 shows the conclusions of the situations for service lines, followed by a detailed elaboration of the individual situations.

Table 4: Conclusions on the effect of permeation on the formation of flammable mixtures in asset service lines

No.	Situation	Conclusion theoretical calculation (appendix I)
5	Branch saddle to valve for the gas meter	When the gas in a PE service line is stagnant and completely disconnected from the rest of the network for a longer period of time, a flammable mixture can develop in 17.4 days. This scenario is considered realistic. It is therefore advisable to take additional safety measures when working and to be aware of this when starting up appliances (see elaboration below for specific recommendations).
6	Service line in casing pipe	In the scenario where a PE casing pipe is completely sealed gas-tight (non-ventilated) around a PE service line, a flammable mixture can develop within 3 hours to 17 days (depending on the chosen dimensions and pressure). However, ordinary facade-penetrating casing pipes are in principle sufficiently open, so that no accumulation of hydrogen can occur. In this situation, permeation therefore does not pose a safety risk [1].
7	Service line permeates to the environment (branch saddle to main valve for the gas meter)	The hydrogen will spread through the soil and escape to the environment. The concentration of hydrogen is in all scenarios well below the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air. Permeation of hydrogen through main lines to the environment will therefore not pose a safety risk for the scenarios with assumptions of this study.

In a service line section from branch saddle to valve, a flammable mixture may possibly occur due to permeation ([5](#))

Situation sketch and assumptions

When residents are away from home for a longer period of time and there is no gas consumption, or the valve for the gas meter is turned off, hydrogen can remain stagnant in the service line for a quite some time. In this situation, it is assumed that the service line is completely closed off from the rest of the gas network. Exchange of gases with other parts of the network does not take place with this assumption.

Results

In a PE service line with the smallest diameter (DN 20) and a pressure of 40 mbar(o) a flammable mixture can form after **17.4 days** in the most critical situation¹⁸. When the pressure is increased to 100 mbar(o), this takes a little longer, **18.1 days**. For the least critical situation¹⁹ the time that must elapse before a flammable mixture has formed increases to **115.8 days**. All other possible situations with other DN, operating pressure and wall thickness lie between the two extremes.

Conclusion and possible measures

The calculation is based on a service line that is completely disconnected from the network. In reality, a service line will still be in contact with the main line. This makes exchange of gases possible by means of flow or diffusion. It is not known what the influence of this open connection is on the chance of a flammable mixture forming within a service line. Practical measurements will have to be carried out to fill this gap. In this study, it cannot be completely ruled out that a flammable mixture can form in a service line. This scenario is therefore assessed as realistic. Possible safety risks during (maintenance) activities on the line can be addressed by listing the risks in the work instructions. In addition, it can be considered to first make the line gas-free and flare it with a (mini) flare with flame arrester. Preventive flushing before carrying out activities is also an option.

In the case of a service line in a casing pipe, a flammable mixture may possibly arise due to permeation (6)

Situation sketch and assumptions

In this situation, an uninterrupted casing pipe for pipes leading into homes is considered, which leads through a non-ventilated hollow space. The casing pipe consists of one piece and is assumed to be sealed gas-tight (non-ventilated) for the calculation to be possible. Outside the facade, the pipe end is sealed, and there are no ventilation openings. The end of the casing pipe ending in the house is also completely sealed.

Results

When the casing pipe is completely sealed gas-tight, a flammable mixture can form in the casing within a reasonable amount of time, according to the calculations. In the most critical situation²⁰ with a PE service line, a flammable mixture can form after **0.1 days**. For a less critical situation²¹ when a casing pipe with a larger diameter is used, this can increase to **17 days**.

Conclusion and possible measures

The calculation is based on a completely gas-tight casing pipe; hydrogen and oxygen cannot leave the space between the gas line and the casing pipe. In reality, the casing pipe is never sealed gas-tight. NEN 7244-1 section 7.4.2.5 stipulates: "A leak in the gas-carrying pipe in the casing pipe must be detectable". In practice, this means that the casing pipe is not sealed gas-tight within the facade, so that the leak can be observed. The opening allows for the exchange of gases (hydrogen, oxygen, but also nitrogen) in the casing pipe and the surrounding area. In addition to the casing pipe not being completely gas-tight, the gases can also permeate through the casing pipe's wall. These processes influence the composition of the mixture in the casing pipe. Ordinary facade-penetrating casing pipes are in principle sufficiently open, so that no accumulation of hydrogen can occur. In this situation, permeation therefore does not pose a safety risk [1].

¹⁸PE - 20mm - 2.3mm - 1.04 bar

¹⁹PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.1 bar

²⁰(B) PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 25 mm - 2.3 mm ('B' indicates the gas pipe, 'M' the casing pipe)

²¹(B) PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 63 mm - 3.8 mm

In case of permeation of a service line to the environment, no flammable mixture is present (7)

Situation sketch and assumptions

By distributing hydrogen gas via the current natural gas distribution network, hydrogen gas will permeate through the pipe wall to the environment. This hydrogen will spread through the soil and escape to the environment.

Results

Even for the most critical situations, it is not possible to create a flammable mixture in the environment above service line, according to the calculation. Above a PE service line a concentration of $1.8 \cdot 10^{-5}\%$ hydrogen in air can occur at ground level in the most critical situation²². For the least critical situation²³ the concentration drops to $0.84 \cdot 10^{-5}\%$.

Conclusion and possible measures

The concentration of hydrogen is in all situations well below the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air (4%). Permeation of hydrogen to the environment will therefore not pose a safety risk for the scenarios and assumptions of this study.

1.3 In all situations, caution is required when working on the technical installation of gas pressure and regulations stations

For the asset gas pressure and regulation stations, three situations have been identified for which the concentration profile of hydrogen and oxygen by permeation has been modeled. These are:

- The formation of a flammable mixture in the section between the separating valves on either side of the station including the technical installation (situation 8).
- The formation of a flammable mixture in the technical installation blocked between the inlet and outlet valve (situation 9).
- The formation of a flammable mixture in a control station that is not used for a long period of time (double-street station) (situation 10).

There is a chance that in all three situations a flammable mixture will be created by permeation over time. When carrying out (maintenance) activities on stations, extra attention is therefore required. table 5 shows the conclusions of the situations for stations, followed by a detailed elaboration of the individual situations.

Table 5: Conclusions on the effect of permeation on the formation of flammable mixtures in asset stations

No	Situation	Conclusion theoretical calculation (appendix I)
8	Station blocked between isolation valve(s)	In the situation where a HAS or AS is blocked unilaterally to disconnect a customer and it is decided to keep the station pressurized, sufficient time can elapse for a flammable mixture to develop in the pipes: 70 days for a HAS, 109 days for an AS. It is therefore advisable to take additional safety measures when carrying out (maintenance) activities (see elaboration below for specific recommendations).

²²PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.1 bar

²³PE - 20mm - 2.3mm - 1.04 bar

		For DS , this blocking is only done consciously for maintenance work. During maintenance work, the closed parts are back in operation within a day. Within 24 hours, no flammable mixture can form in the installation in this section for a single-lane and double-lane DS due to permeation. In this case, permeation does not constitute a potential safety risk.
9	Technical installation blocked between the inlet valve (and outlet valve)	For (maintenance) activities on the technical installation of a station, the technical installation is also blocked between the inlet and outlet valves of the installation. This short blockage of max. a few hours is not sufficient to create a flammable mixture in the pipe. For this, 5.4 days for HAS, 6.4 days for AS and 82 days for DS must pass for the worst case scenarios. Due to the falling of a safety valve, it is possible that the installation of a HAS or DS is blocked on one side. In the time that elapses until the next maintenance service, a flammable mixture can arise in the installation due to permeation at DS and HAS. It is therefore advisable to take additional safety measures during (maintenance) activities (see elaboration below for specific recommendations).
10	Single control line (Spare control line of double control line)	The inactive control line of a double line installation of an AS or DS may not be used for a long period of time (months) and may be disconnected from the rest of the network. If we disregard the mixing of hydrogen and oxygen in the reserve street with the rest of the outgoing network, there is a chance that after 6.4 days (AS) and 82 days (DS) a flammable mixture will be created and will be present when (maintenance) activities are subsequently carried out. It is therefore advisable to take additional safety measures when carrying out (maintenance) activities (see elaboration below for specific recommendations).

In the technical installation of a station blocked between the isolation valve(s), a flammable mixture can arise through permeation (8)

Situation sketch and assumptions

When working on the technical installation of stations, or for removal or replacement, a station is closed by closing the isolation valves on both sides of the station. This closing can also occur when removing or replacing a station. In addition, it is possible that a HAS or AS that serves a single customer can be blocked on one side. For this situation, it is assumed that permeation through the rubber (NBR) membrane of a regulator can take place. This membrane is in contact with the gas in the outgoing pipe of the station. Therefore, the technical installation and 10 meters of pipe up to the isolation valves after the station are assumed as a section here. For the steel pipe sections, it is assumed that permeation is minimal and negligible.

Results

In the outgoing line of a typical HAS 25 with the lowest pressure and largest diaphragm surface, a flammable mixture can form after 70 days in the most critical situation²⁴. Increasing the pressure leads to less critical situations with the least critical situation²⁵ being the formation of a flammable mixture after **708 days** (see table 6). Table 6 indicates the time that must elapse before flammable mixtures have formed in the outgoing line of a typical AS 100, single-pass and double-pass DS 2500. All other possible situations with other outlet pressures and diaphragm surfaces between the selected sizes lie between the two extremes of each station.

Table 6: Time required for a flammable mixture to form by permeation in the outgoing line of a typical station blocked between isolation valves

Type of station	Most critical situation	Least critical situation
HAS 25	70 days	708 days
AS 100	109 days ²⁶	1062 days (almost 3 years) ²⁹
DS 2500 (single street)	1120 days (over 3 years) ²⁷	9350 days (over 25.5 years) ³⁰
DS 2500 (double street)	600 days (more than 1.5 years) ²⁸	5005 days (over 13.5 years) ³¹

Conclusion and possible measures

For delivery stations and house connection sets, it is very likely that only one customer is supplied with gas by the station. The installation of these stations is checked once every 2 years (AS), and once every 5 years or possibly not at all (HAS). In the situation where a HAS or AS is blocked on one side to disconnect a customer and it is decided to keep the station under pressure, sufficient time can elapse for a flammable mixture to develop in the pipes. This situation is therefore a realistic scenario for HAS and AS. For district stations, multiple customers are connected to them and annual inspections are carried out. This section will only be deliberately closed for maintenance activities. During maintenance activities, the closed parts will be operational again within one day. Within 24 hours, no flammable mixture can develop in the installation in this section due to permeation in a single-lane and double-lane DS. Possible safety risks during (maintenance) activities on stations can be addressed by listing the risks in the work instructions. In addition, it may be considered to flare the contents of the pipe with a (mini) flare with flame arrester before starting to work. To prevent oxygen from entering the installation via the diaphragm of the regulator, an impermeable alternative could be considered – in case available.

In the technical installation of a station blocked between the inlet valve (and outlet valve), a flammable mixture can arise through permeation (9)

Situation sketch and assumptions

For (maintenance) activities on the technical installation of a station, the technical installation is also blocked between the inlet and outlet valves of the installation. In addition, it can happen that a fallen safety remains unnoticed for a long time. For this situation, it is assumed that permeation through the rubber membrane of a regulator can take place. This membrane is in contact with the gas in the

²⁴NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

²⁵NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 8 bar

²⁶NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

²⁷NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

²⁸NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

²⁹NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 8 bar

³⁰NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 4 bar

³¹NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 4 bar

outgoing pipe of the station. Therefore, the section is assumed to be from regulator to the outlet valve. For the steel pipe sections, it is assumed that permeation is minimal and negligible.

Results

In the outgoing line of a typical HAS 25 with lowest pressure and largest diaphragm area, a flammable mixture can form after **5.4 days** in the most critical situation³². Increasing the pressure leads to less critical situations with the least critical situation³³ being the formation of a flammable mixture after **55.5 days**. Table 7 shows the time that must elapse before flammable mixtures have formed in the outgoing line of a typical AS 100 and DS 2500. All other possible situations with other outlet pressures and diaphragm areas between the selected sizes lie between the two extremes of each station.

Table 7: Time required for a flammable mixture to form by permeation in the outgoing line of a typical station blocked between inlet and outlet valves

Type of station	Most critical situation	Least critical situation
HAS 25	5.4 days ³⁴	55.5 days ³⁷
AS 100	6.4 days ³⁵	64 days ³⁸
DS 2500	82 days ³⁶	684 days ³⁹ (almost 2 years)

Conclusion and possible measures

For delivery stations (AS), only one customer is served by the station and the installation is checked once a year. For high-pressure delivery stations (HAS), it is possible that one or more customers are served by the station. The installation is checked once every 5 years or possibly not at all. For district stations, multiple customers are connected to it and annual inspections are carried out. This section will only be deliberately closed for maintenance work for DS, AS, and HAS. During maintenance work, the closed parts are back in operation within a day. Within 24 hours, no flammable mixture can develop in the installation due to permeation in this section. However, in the case of HAS or DS, it can also happen that the installation is blocked on one side due to a safety valve falling. Because the supply is received by other stations (due to over dimensioning of the network), this may not be noticed until the next inspection. In the worst case, this section will then be idle for a year for DS and several years in the case of HAS. In these cases, it is possible that permeation at DS 2500 and HAS 25 will create a flammable mixture in the installation, and is therefore a realistic scenario. Possible safety risks during (maintenance) activities on stations can be addressed by listing the risks in the work instructions. Opening the safety valve in this situation will ensure flow and expel the mixture from the installation.

In a single control line (reserve control line of double control line) a flammable mixture may possibly arise due to permeation (10)

Situation sketch and assumptions

The gas pressure regulation system can include multiple control lines to increase the security of supply. Stations with double-line installations have the advantage that automatic switching takes place in the event of faults and the gas supply is better guaranteed. The inactive control line of a double-line installation cannot be used for a longer period of time (months) and be disconnected

³²NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

³³NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 8 bar

³⁴NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

³⁵NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

³⁶NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

³⁷NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 8 bar

³⁸NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 8 bar

³⁹NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 4 bar

from the rest of the network. For this situation, it is assumed that permeation through the rubber membrane of a regulator can take place. This membrane is in contact with the gas in the outgoing pipe of the station. Therefore, the section is assumed to be from regulator to the outlet valve. For the steel pipe sections, it is assumed that permeation is minimal and negligible.

Results

In the outgoing line of a typical AS 100 with the lowest pressure and the largest diaphragm surface, a flammable mixture can form after **6.4 days** in the most critical situation⁴⁰. When the pressure is increased and the diaphragm surface is reduced in a less critical situation⁴¹ the time until a flammable mixture has formed increases to **64 days**. In the outgoing line of a typical DS 2500 with the lowest pressure and the largest diaphragm surface, a flammable mixture can form after **82 days** in the most critical situation⁴². In a less critical situation⁴³ with a higher outlet pressure and smaller diaphragm surface, the time can increase to **684 days** (almost 2 years). All other possible situations with other outlet pressures and diaphragm surfaces between the selected sizes lie between the two extremes.

Conclusion and possible measures

For delivery stations and district stations, the installation including the non-operational street is checked annually. It is therefore not inconceivable that there will be no gas flow in a reserve control street for a few months to a maximum. If we assume that it is a closed section, there is a chance that after 6.4 days (AS) and 82 days (DS) a flammable mixture will be created and will be present when activities are subsequently carried out. This volume will be small due to the influence of mixing with the underlying network. These situations are assessed to be a realistic scenario. Possible safety risks during (maintenance) activities on stations can be addressed by listing the risks in the work instructions. In addition, it can be considered to flare the contents of the pipe with a (mini) flare with flame arrester before starting (maintenance) activities.

2. Recommendations

Safety in management and use of the gas distribution network is always top priority for the Dutch gas distribution network operators in order to minimize risks to people and the environment. Extensive research is being conducted into safety for the future distribution of hydrogen. This includes attention to the formation of a flammable mixture in pipelines and casing pipes due to permeation of hydrogen and oxygen. Permeation is a natural and unavoidable process. Due to concentration differences on either side of the pipe wall of gas pipelines, the transported gases will permeate from the pipe to casing pipes and the environment. Conversely, oxygen from the environment will enter the pipe.

This study has provided initial insight into the probability of a flammable mixture occurring in various situations. It has been shown that a flammable mixture could be expected in various situations. The presence of an ignition source due to static can be ruled out in all situations where a flammable hydrogen-oxygen mixture is present. Due to the absence of flow, static charge due to dust transport cannot build up. This study provides recommendations for (maintenance) work on hydrogen networks. In addition recommendations are made for investigating several situations in practice with practical tests.

⁴⁰NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

⁴¹NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 8 bar

⁴²NBR - Ø28.00 - 1 mm - 0.1 bar

⁴³NBR - Ø12,25 - 1 mm - 4 bar

Measures for maintenance activities on hydrogen distribution networks

This study identifies five situations in which permeation may result in a flammable mixture that may still be present when (maintenance) activities are carried out. The safety measures that require extra attention and which can be taken when carrying out maintenance work on these sections are listed below. In addition, recommendations are made to test the theory behind the identified risky scenarios.

1. The scenario in which a flammable hydrogen-air mixture is present in a PE or PVC casing pipe around a main line, which could have arisen through permeation, and after which (maintenance) activities are carried out, is considered realistic. It is very likely that a flammable mixture can be present at least in the middle of the casing pipe. It is therefore advisable to:
 - list possible safety risks during (maintenance) activities on the pipeline in the work instructions.
 - determine, prior to carrying out (maintenance) activities, using gas measuring equipment, that the gas concentration is low enough to allow safe working.
 - investigate the usefulness of mandatory flushing or blowing through of the casing prior to carrying out work.
2. The scenario in which a flammable mixture is present in the service line between the branch saddle and the tap for the gas meter due to prolonged stagnant gas is considered realistic. In reality, the service line will still be in contact with the main line, which allows for exchange of gases by means of flow or diffusion. It is not known exactly what the influence of this exchange is on the chance of a flammable mixture forming in the service line. Therefore, this study cannot completely rule out the possibility that a flammable mixture can form in a service line and this scenario is realistic. This could potentially pose a safety risk during (maintenance) activities, but could also have negative consequences for starting up appliances. It is therefore recommended to:
 - list possible safety risks during (maintenance) activities on the pipeline in the work instructions.
 - consider the option of making the pipeline gas-free and flaring it with a (mini) flare with flame arrester, or preventive flushing before (maintenance) activities are done.
 - investigate the consequences of a flammable mixture for the operation of consumer appliances.
3. The scenario in which a flammable mixture is present due to permeation over the membrane surface of a regulator in the outgoing line of a unilaterally blocked HAS or AS (by closing the isolating valve) is realistic. It is therefore recommended to:
 - specify the safety risks during (maintenance) activities on gas pressure reduction and regulation stations in the work instructions.
 - to investigate the usefulness of flaring the contents of the line with a (mini) flare with flame arrester before starting (maintenance) activities.
4. The scenario in which a flammable mixture is present through permeation over the membrane surface of a regulator in the outgoing line of a unilaterally blocked HAS or DS (by falling of a safety device) is realistic. It is therefore recommended to:
 - specify the safety risks during (maintenance) activities on gas pressure reduction and regulation stations in the work instructions.
 - to investigate the usefulness of flaring the contents of the line with a (mini) flare with flame arrester before starting (maintenance) activities.

5. The scenario where a small volume of flammable mixture is present through permeation across the membrane surface of a regulator in the outgoing line of a reserve control line of an AS or DS is realistic. It is therefore recommended to:
 - list safety risks during (maintenance) activities on gas pressure reduction and regulation stations in the work instructions.
 - and to investigate whether it is necessary to blow off the contents of the pipe before starting work or to flare it with a (mini) flare with flame arrester.

Practical measurements must prove actual chance of flammable mixture

The actual probability of a flammable mixture occurring in a section of the gas distribution network may deviate from the estimates in this study due to the boundary conditions of the calculation.

These boundary conditions are necessary to make the calculation possible. They simplify the calculation making the results a simplification of reality. Some important factors that influence the composition of the gas mixture are the influence of:

- nitrogen entry on the flammability of a mixture;
- effect of the presence of surrounding soil (moisture content, ventilation) and the moisture content of the pipe on the permeation rate of gases (hydrogen, oxygen and nitrogen);
- distribution of gases (oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) by diffusion or flow to the nearby gas network and reserve control lines of gas pressure reduction and regulation stations;
- distribution of gases (oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) in the meter box from the opening in facade-penetrating casing pipes, and through the rubber end seals and the soil for casing pipes of main lines;
- permeation of gases (oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) through the casing pipe wall to the environment;
- the addition of hydrogen in service lines in the event of a pressure drop in a network that is not completely separated from the distribution network;
- the type of rubber of the regulator diaphragm;
- other rubber elements and metal components in stations;
- the design of the regulator including the influence of the membrane surface and the metal plates on permeation and ventilation (gas composition above the membrane).
- The material of the pipe. This study focuses on the worst case situations: gas lines made of plastic. For more insight into the effect of permeation for other materials, for example main lines made of steel, a PEKO service line in a casing pipe, or PE-X pipes, more research is necessary.

It is possible, that these influences cause, for example, a flammable mixture to develop later, or perhaps not at all. Another possibility is that the flammable volume in relation to the non-flammable volume differs per location in the pipe, casing pipe or station. As a result, it is also not inconceivable that only a small amount ignites during ignition and the reaction then stops. The concentrations of hydrogen in oxygen in the situations can also differ, and with that the possible effects of ignition. The effect of ignition cannot be estimated with the method in this report. In order to provide an even better picture of the Dutch practical situation and the chance of a flammable mixture developing, possible effects and the risks, practical tests will have to be carried out. This is also necessary for formulating appropriate measures for (maintenance) activities.

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Appendix I – Methods and boundary conditions

Permeation is a natural and unavoidable process in which a permeate (a gas, vapor or liquid) moves through a physical barrier layer, such as a pipeline wall. The permeation process is driven by a difference in concentration of the permeate. In the case of gas lines, this is the difference between the gas concentrations that prevail on either side of the pipe wall. As a result of the higher concentration of hydrogen inside the pipe, hydrogen will permeate from inside the gas network to the outside. Conversely, oxygen can permeate from the atmosphere through the pipe wall into the gas network. The permeation process can potentially lead to the formation of a flammable mixture in pipelines, casing pipes or the environment. Permeation is a different phenomenon than leakage. In a leak, the physical barrier that separates the contents of the pipe from the environment is missing.

In order to estimate whether situations can occur in which flammable mixtures are present in the gas network when (maintenance) activities are being carried out, a model was made. This model assesses when the upper and lower flammability limits are reached within a gas line, casing pipe or station. In addition, a reasoning was made to estimate the chance of a flammable mixture arising through permeation at ground level. Setting boundary conditions is essential to be able to do this without CFD and practical calculations. In this way, a simplified version of reality is obtained. It is necessary to take note of the boundary conditions and assumptions that have been made in order to make an estimate regarding the chance of obtaining a flammable mixture. The two methods and associated boundary conditions and assumptions are explained in the paragraphs below.

Method pipes, casings and stations

The time that must elapse before a flammable mixture is created in a situation (selected pipe section) is determined on the basis of pressure differences of the gases over time. Basically, we are looking for the moment at which a flammability limit is exceeded. This is typically expressed in a concentration ratio ($H_2 : O_2$). The concentrations used in the calculation can be found in the paragraph “Flammability limits of hydrogen-oxygen mixtures and hydrogen-air mixtures”. Because we assume that we are dealing with an ideal gas, the concentration difference may be replaced by a difference in pressure. The pressure ratio $P_{H_2} : P_{O_2}$ remains the same as that of the concentration.

The hydrogen pressure that prevails in a pipe at a given moment depends on the initial hydrogen pressure in the pipe minus the pressure decrease due to permeation over a certain time step. The oxygen pressure that prevails in a pipe at a given moment depends on the initial oxygen pressure in the pipe plus the pressure increase due to permeation over a certain time step due to permeation. The following applies to the formation of a flammable hydrogen-oxygen mixture in a pipe:

The following applies to permeation of hydrogen in the gas line to the environment:

$$p_{waterstof}(t) = p_{waterstof}(0) \cdot e^{\frac{-P_c \cdot A}{V_b \cdot e} \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t}$$

The following applies to permeation of oxygen from the environment to the gas line:

$$p_{zuurstof}(t) = p(O_2) + p(O_2) \cdot e^{\frac{-P_c \cdot A}{V_b \cdot e} \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot t}$$

With:

- $p_{\text{hydrogen}}(t)$ the hydrogen pressure in the tube at time (t) in days;
- $p_{\text{hydrogen}}(0)$ the initial hydrogen pressure in the line in bar(a);
- $p_{\text{oxygen}}(t)$ the oxygen pressure in the tube at time (t) in days;
- $p_{\text{oxygen}}(0_2)$ the oxygen pressure in air (21% of air pressure) in bar;
- P_c is the permeability coefficient in (ml·mm)/(m²·bar·day);
- A is the surface area in m²;
- V_b the volume of the pipe in m³;
- e the wall thickness in mm;
- t is the elapsed time in days.

The moment at which the pressures $p_{\text{hydrogen}}(t)$ and $p_{\text{oxygen}}(t)$ reach the ratio of the upper flammability limit is equal to the number of days the pipe section must be closed before a flammable mixture can form. If the period of isolation from the network can occur before (maintenance) activities are carried out, it is a flammable mixture might be present in the pipe due to permeation.

To determine the period that must elapse before a flammable mixture is in the casing pipe or station, the above equations have been adjusted to describe those situations.

Method environment

By distributing hydrogen gas via the current natural gas distribution network, hydrogen gas will permeate through the pipe wall to the environment. This escaping gas has effects on the environment. In [2] the diffusion of hydrogen in the soil and the effect at ground level were investigated. At a depth of 0.8 m, a leaking tube was installed with a hole of approximately 1 mm in diameter. A hose was connected to this tube and a leak of 120.2 l/h hydrogen was created. The spread of the underground dosed leak gas was then measured in three directions using a gas detection mat, bell jar and soil probe. table 8 shows the results of the measurements directly above the leak. Over the entire range, the measured values for the soil probe are higher than for the bell jar and the leak detection mat.

Table 8: measured hydrogen concentration with three different measurement equipment [2]

Measuring apparatus	Measured concentration (%)
Soil probe	5
Bell jar	3.75
Gas detection mat	0.1

The leak size of 120 l/h in combination with the concentration of 5% (worst case) measured by the soil probe is used to estimate the effect of permeation at ground level. The permeation rate (Q) is determined for 1 meter of PE or PVC pipe using the formula below. It is assumed that the hydrogen that escapes over a meter of pipe length ends up in its entirety in the air that is taken in by the soil probe.

$$Q = \frac{P_c \cdot A \cdot \Delta p}{e}$$

With:

- Q is the permeation rate in ml/day;
- P_c is the permeability coefficient in (ml·mm)/(m²·bar·day);
- A is the surface area in m²;
- Δp is the partial pressure difference of the permeate on either side of the pipe wall in bar;
- and the wall thickness in mm.

The permeation rate is then translated into the concentration that [2] would be present at the ground level at a leak size of the permeation rate found using the calculation below.

$$C_{\text{permeatie}} = \frac{Q_{\text{permeatie}} \cdot C_{\text{sonde}}}{Q_{\text{sonde}}}$$

With:

- $C_{\text{permeation}}$ the concentration by permeation at ground level (%)
- $Q_{\text{permeation}}$ the permeation rate of 1m pipe in ml/h
- C_{probe} the concentration due to leakage at ground level (%)
- Q_{probe} the leak size of the probe in ml/h

When the concentration by permeation ($C_{\text{permeation}}$) exceeds the lower flammability limit, the probability of the presence of a flammable mixture is indicated as almost certain. Concentrations that do not come close to this make the probability impossible.

Boundary conditions and assumptions for calculations

For the calculation, several parameters were varied, including variables such as material, dimensions, partial pressure, permeability coefficients, and ambient conditions. The assumptions are based on standard conditions and representative data from the literature. Below follows an explanation of these parameters, assumptions and background information.

Considered (pipe) materials

For this research it was decided to focus on the pipe materials PE and PVC for permeation situations, supplemented by consideration of some pipe sections with rubber components (diaphragms of regulators and gaskets). This choice was made for the following reasons:

1. The majority of gas pipelines are made of plastic. The Dutch gas distribution network consists of 83% of the plastics PE and PVC (both hard and impact-resistant PVC), compared to 14% steel [4]. The share of grey cast iron and asbestos cement is (<3%). These materials are no longer used for the construction of new networks.
2. Metals have a higher resistance to permeation than plastics. This applies to steel and copper pipes, but also to multilayer pipes with an aluminum intermediate layer (PEX-Al). By considering plastics, the most permeation-sensitive material is investigated.
3. Rubber materials are more sensitive to permeation compared to PE, PVC and steel. Including permeation through rubber parts of components gives a better estimate of the chance of flammable mixtures forming in stations.

Permeability coefficients of (pipe) materials

In previous studies on hydrogen and oxygen permeability coefficients of PVC and PE have been determined (table 9) [1], [5], The worst case values were included in the model. The table has been

supplemented with permeability coefficients for NBR (acrylonitrile rubber), one of the most commonly used rubbers in natural gas systems [6]. The oxygen and hydrogen permeability coefficients found for NBR often give higher values than SBR or HNBR rubbers and therefore also seem to be a worst case. In the situations no account was taken of the influence of couplers. In [1] it has been shown that permeation rates for hydrogen through compounds are comparable to those through a pipe of equal length. The influence of couplers is therefore negligible for the system. The exact humidity at which these permeability coefficients were determined is not known exactly, but lies between 0-70%. The humidity of the substrate and possibly higher moisture content of the pipe wall can influence the permeation rate of gases.

Table 9: Permeability coefficients from literature and previous research of which the most conservative permeability coefficients (bold values) have been selected for calculations in this study.

Gas	Material	Permeability coefficient at 20-25 °C (ml·mm)/(m ² ·bar·day)	Ref
H ₂	PE	Research: MDPE (service line) 191.7- 193.0	[1]
		Research: HDPE 125.2- 179.4	[1]
	PVC	Research: 87.3- 181.3	[1]
	Steel	Literature: 1.51-13.02	[7], [8]
	NBR	Literature: 3188.4	[9]
O ₂	PE	Literature: 38.9- 77.7	[10], [5]
		Research: 41.7-70.6	[5]
	PVC	Literature: 1.93-10.0 (and one source 774) Research: 4.6- 19.1	[11], [10], [5]
	NBR	Literature: 259.2	[9]

Permeation surfaces of pipes and components in gas stations

The most critical situation for the formation of a flammable mixture in the gas pipeline is the situation in which the upper flammability limit is reached most quickly. For casing pipes, the most critical situation is reaching the upper flammability limit in the space between the gas line and casing pipe. For most and least critical situations, this means that assumptions are made for:

- nominal diameter (DN);
- wall thickness (e);
- operating pressure (hydrogen) and oxygen pressure (input for Δp);
- contents of station;
- station permeation surface.

The most and least critical nominal diameters and wall thicknesses have been determined using NEN-EN 1555-2:2021 (PE) and NEN 7230:2020 (PVC). The oxygen pressure is assumed to be 21% of the air pressure (0.21 bar(o)). The maximum and minimum operating pressures, in consultation with the guidance group, are the maximum and minimum pressures below (

table 10). The diaphragm of the regulator of stations is in contact with the outgoing pipe of a station. Therefore, the pipe pressure in the outgoing pipe (P_u) has been assumed for stations.

Table 10: Assumed minimum and maximum pressures of pipe sections

Pipe section and material	Pressure (bar(o))
PE main line	0.1-8
PVC main line	0.1
PE service line	0.04-0.1
DS 2500, AS 100, HAS 25	0.1-8

The contents of stations have been estimated using technical drawings of a typical AS 100, DS 2500 and HAS 25. The contents of stations between the regulator to the ground and separator valve are shown in table 11.

Table 11: Volume of the installation of DS 2500 and AS 100 from the regulator to the outlet and separator valve

Station	Volume of line between regulator and isolating valve (m ³)	Volume of pipe between regulator and separator valve (m ³)
DS 2500	0.025	0.339
AS 100	0.0019	0.0331
HAS 25	0.0017	0.0213

In gas stations, rubber components (including gaskets and membranes) are more sensitive to permeation than steel pipes. For the permeation surface in the calculations with stations, it has therefore been assumed that permeation of steel components and pipes is negligible. In addition, permeation only takes place over the surface of the membrane of the regulator. The influence of gaskets and other rubber components in measuring instruments has not been included. An estimate of the membrane surface has been made for three different regulators (table 12). In practice, a large part of the membrane is enclosed between two metal plates. For the calculation, it has been assumed that these plates have no influence on the surface over which permeation takes place and that the space between the membrane and the plates is well ventilated (hydrogen cannot accumulate).

Table 12: Estimated membrane area used for calculation

Regulator	Surface area membrane (m ²)
Small	0.0233
Medium	0.0657
Big	0.1056

Flammability limits of hydrogen-oxygen mixtures and hydrogen-air mixtures

For a gas mixture to be flammable, a certain ratio of gas:oxygen or gas:air must be present. The lower flammability limit is the concentration of a flammable gas in oxygen/air below which the mixture no longer burns independently (due to lack of fuel). The upper flammability limit is the concentration of a flammable gas in air above which the mixture no longer burns (due to lack of oxygen). Figure 1 shows the flammability limits of a hydrogen-air mixture.

Figure 1: Flammability limits for a hydrogen-air mixture

In a pipe with ~100% hydrogen, the upper flammability limit will be reached first by permeation of hydrogen out of the pipe and oxygen in the pipe. For the upper flammability limit, the ratio of hydrogen:oxygen in the flammable mixture is assumed to be 95.2:4.8. This is the highest flammability limit found in literature [12], [13](table 13). The permeation of nitrogen is not included in the calculations. Nitrogen may have an inhibiting effect and therefore result in a small shift in the upper flammability limit. With the ratio 95.2:4.8 we assume a worst case situation.

Table 13: Upper flammability limits of hydrogen-air mixtures and hydrogen-oxygen mixtures at room temperature according to various sources

Upper flammability limit (H ₂ :O ₂)	Pressure and temperature	Reference
94.75 : 5.25 ⁴⁴	unknown	[14], [15], [16]
95.2 : 4.8	1 bar, 20 °C	[12], [13]
94.6 : 5.4	5 bar, 20 °C	
94.2 : 5.8	10 bar, 20 °C	
94.0 : 6.0	unknown	[17], [18]

In a casing pipe, 100% air is initially present. By permeation of hydrogen from the gas line to the casing tube, the lower flammability limit will be reached first. For the lower flammability limit of hydrogen in air, the ratio 4.0 : 96, the highest ratio found in literature, has been used (table 14).

Table 14: Lower flammability limits of hydrogen-air mixtures and hydrogen-oxygen mixtures at room temperature according to various sources

Lower flammability limit (H ₂ :air)	pressure and temperature	reference
4.0 : 96	unknown	[14], [15], [16]
4.1 : 95.9	1 bar	[17]

Conditions in gas lines and casing pipes

For the formation of a flammable mixture in a pipe, it is assumed that the pipe contains 100% hydrogen and is completely closed off from the rest of the gas distribution network. As a result, mixing of hydrogen and oxygen with the rest of the network by diffusion or flow cannot take place. This also means that no hydrogen or oxygen can permeate or leak through an inflatable gas stopper,

⁴⁴Determined on the basis of hydrogen-air mixture. The upper flammability limit is reached when 75% vol H₂ and 25% vol air are present. Air consists of approximately 78% nitrogen and 21% oxygen. 21% of the 25% (5.25%) is therefore oxygen.

valve or regulator valve. The hydrogen in the gas line after a section has been closed off can only leave the pipe by permeation. Oxygen can permeate the pipe from the environment via the pipe wall. With the method used, we create a pressure drop in the gas line for the situations of a flammable mixture in the pipe. This is simply because the permeation of oxygen into the pipe is slower than that of hydrogen out of the pipe. In reality, the pressure drop will have to be compensated for in some way. In those situations where the pipe section in question is not completely closed off from the rest of the network, this can be done by adding hydrogen.

For the formation of a flammable mixture in a casing pipe that serves as a feed-through for a main line or service line, it is assumed that the casing pipe is not ventilated. The oxygen that is between the casing pipe and the gas line can permeate the gas pipe, but does not escape and is not replenished from the environment by the casing pipe wall or sealing sleeves. In other words, the rubber sleeves with which a casing pipe of a main line is sealed and the casing pipe are assumed to be impermeable. For a facade-penetrating casing pipe, this means that it is assumed that it is sealed gas-tight in the meter box and that this seal and casing pipe are impermeable.

Environmental conditions soil and atmosphere

It is assumed that the pipe in which the flammable mixture is formed is completely surrounded by air on the outside. The environment (soil and atmosphere) is well ventilated. Therefore, there is no accumulation of permeated hydrogen gas outside the pipe, and there is no change in the percentage of oxygen in the air. The effects of any capillary water, cracks, and obstacles in the soil are excluded, as well as other forms of soil types, soil stratification, and soil inhomogeneity. It is also assumed that there is no non-gas-permeable layer such as asphalt, rubble, or decorative paving.

In practice, the presence of moist soil or groundwater affects the moisture content of pipelines. The moisture content can affect the permeation rate of gases. The permeability coefficients are determined in dry conditions and are therefore a worst-case situation. In addition, pipelines assume the temperature of the soil. In the Netherlands, the soil temperature at a depth of 100 cm is between 5 °C and 18 °C, and is on average approximately 11 °C [19]. For the flammability limits and permeability coefficients, a temperature of 20-25 °C has been taken into account, which may be seen as a worst-case situation.

Appendix II – Calculation example of hydrogen permeation in a steel pipe

For the steel pipes that are used in practice for the transport of natural gas, and possibly in the future for the transport of hydrogen gas, the comparison was made with 4130 steel (normally annealed) [7] and 1020 steel (normally annealed) [8]. The permeation rate of hydrogen was determined at:

- A pipe with the dimensions according to NEN 7244-3:2016:
 - Nominal diameter (DN) 100;
 - External diameter 114.3 mm;
 - Nominal wall thickness 3.6 mm;
 - A length of 1 m.

From these dimensions it follows that permeation can take place over an area of:

$$A = \pi(0,1143 - 0,0036) \cdot 1 = 0,3478 \text{ m}^2$$

- With the circumstances:
 - An internal hydrogen pressure of 9 bar(a) (8 bar(o));
 - An external hydrogen pressure of 0 bar(a);
 - At a temperature of 20 °C.

This gives a permeation rate for 4130 steel (normally annealed) [7]:

$$Q = \frac{P_{C,M} \cdot A \cdot (\sqrt{P_i} - \sqrt{P_o})}{e} = \frac{1,51 \cdot 0,3478 \cdot (\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{0})}{3,6} = 0,436 \frac{\text{ml}}{\text{dag}}$$

Converted, this is equal to 0.159 m³ per km per year.

This gives a permeation rate for 1020 steel (normally annealed) [8]:

$$Q = \frac{P_{C,M} \cdot A \cdot (\sqrt{P_i} - \sqrt{P_o})}{e} = \frac{13,02 \cdot 0,3478 \cdot (\sqrt{9} - \sqrt{0})}{3,6} = 3,77 \frac{\text{ml}}{\text{dag}}$$

Converted, this is equal to 1.38 m³ per km per year.

For reference, under gas distribution conditions the permeation rate of plastic pipes (PVC, HDPE, MDPE) varies from 4.0 to 17.1 m³ per km per year, see the report '[Permeation of hydrogen](#)'. Note that other conditions have been taken into account, such as other hydrogen pressures and pipe dimensions.

But with this initial calculation, it turns out that the permeation of hydrogen through steel is roughly a factor of 10 to 100 times lower than for plastic.

Appendix III – Calculated situations

Table 15: Period that must elapse before a flammable mixture has formed for all calculated gas line and casing pipe situations. 'B' indicates the gas pipe, 'M' the casing pipe. And all concentrations for hydrogen in the environment are calculated.

#	Situations	Period elapsed for flammable mixture in the pipe for different situations
1	Main line closed due to blowing	PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 0.1 bar: 118 days PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 8 bar: 411 days PE - 250 mm - 14.8 mm - 0.1 bar: 1843 days PE - 250 mm - 14.8 mm - 8 bar: 6390 days PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar: 155 days PVC - 250 mm - 6.2 mm - 0.1 bar: 1950 days
2	Main line closed between two valves	PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 0.1 bar: 118 days PE - 250 mm - 14.8 mm - 0.1 bar: 1843 days PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar: 155 days PVC - 250 mm - 6.2 mm - 0.1 bar: 1950 days
3	Main line in casing pipe	(B) PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 75 mm - 4.5 mm: 0.15 days (B) PE - 75 mm - 4.5 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 90 mm - 5.4 mm: 0.26 days (B) PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 75 mm - 4.5 mm: 1.3 days (B) PE - 75 mm - 4.5 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 90 mm - 5.4 mm: 2.2 days (B) PE - 200 mm - 11.9 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 250 mm - 14.8 mm: 28.5 days (DN 225 does not fit) If the casing tube is more than 1 size larger: (B) PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 90 mm - 5.4 mm: 0.95 days (B) PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 110 mm - 6.6 mm: 2.2 days (B) PE - 75 mm - 4.5 mm - 8.0 bar + (M) 110 mm - 6.6 mm: 1.6 days (B) PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 75 mm - 2 mm: 1.9 days (B) PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.2 bar + (M) 75 mm - 2 mm: 1.7 days (B) PVC - 75 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 90 mm - 2.2 mm: 2.5 days (B) PVC - 90 mm - 2.2 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 110 mm - 2.7 mm: 3.7 days (B) PVC - (225) mm - 5.5 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 250 mm - 6.2 mm: 7.6 days (B) PVC - (225) mm - 5.5 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 250 mm - 6.2 mm: 7.0 days If the casing tube is more than 1 size larger: (B) PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 90 mm - 2.2 mm: 5.8 days (B) PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 110 mm - 2.7 mm: 12 days (B) PVC - 200 mm - 4.9 mm - 0.1 bar + (M) 250 mm - 6.2 mm: 21.5 days
4	Main line permeates to environment	PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 0.1 bar: 0.0000167 % H ₂ PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 8 bar: 0.0001370 % H ₂ PE - 250 mm - 14.8 mm - 0.1 bar: 0.0000171 % H ₂ PE - 250 mm - 14.8 mm - 8 bar: 0.0001397 % H ₂ PVC - 63 mm - 2 mm - 0.1 bar: 0.0000331 % H ₂ PVC - 250 mm - 6.2 mm - 0.1 bar: 0.0000427 % H ₂ PVC - 250 mm - 6.2 mm - 0.2 bar: 0.0000466 % H ₂

5	Branch saddle to tap for the gas meter	<p>PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.04 bar: 17.4 days (Pc MDPE), 17.8 days (Pc PE) PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar: 18.1 days PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.04 bar: 32.8 days PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar: 34.2 days (Upper detonation limit - 93.7:6.3) PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar: 42 days (Stoichiometric mixture - 85.2:14.8) PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar: 75.6 days PE - 40 mm - 2.4 mm - 1.04 bar: 44.4 days PE - 40 mm - 2.4 mm - 1.1 bar: 46.2 days PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.04 bar: 111 days PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.1 bar: 115.8 days</p>
6	Service line in casing pipe	<p>PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.04 bar - (M) 25 mm - 2.3 mm: 0.11 days PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 25 mm - 2.3 mm: 0.10 days PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.04 bar - (M) 40 mm - 2.4 mm: 0.87 days PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 40 mm - 2.4 mm: 0.82 days PE - 40 mm - 2.4 mm - 1.04 bar - (M) 50 mm - 3.0 mm: 1.10 days PE - 40 mm - 2.4 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 50 mm - 3.0 mm: 1.05 days PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.04 bar - (M) 75 mm - 4.5 mm: 1.30 days PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 75 mm - 4.5 mm: 1.22 days</p> <p>If the casing tube is more than 1 size larger: PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 32 mm - 2.3 mm: 2.24 days PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 63 mm - 3.8 mm: 17 days PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 63 mm - 3.8 mm: 7.8 days PE - 40 mm - 2.4 mm - 1.1 bar - (M) 63 mm - 3.8 mm: 4.6 days</p>
7	Service line permeates to the environment (branch saddle to main tap for the gas meter)	<p>PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.04 bar: 0.0000084 % H₂ PE - 20 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar: 0.0000089 % H₂ PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.04 bar: 0.0000141 % H₂ PE - 32 mm - 2.3 mm - 1.1 bar: 0.0000149 % H₂ PE - 40 mm - 2.4 mm - 1.04 bar: 0.0000171 % H₂ PE - 40 mm - 2.4 mm - 1.1 bar: 0.0000181 % H₂ PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.04 bar: 0.0000170 % H₂ PE - 63 mm - 3.8 mm - 1.1 bar: 0.0000180 % H₂</p>
8	Gas station blocked between isolation valve(s)	<p><u>DS 2500</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 4890 days / 13.4 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 5068 days / 13.8 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 9350 days / 25.6 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 1740 days / 4,8 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 1800 days / 4,93 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 3320 days / 9,1 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 1086 days / 2,98 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 1120 days / 3,07 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 2064 days / 5,65 years</p> <p><u>Double Street DS 2500</u> NBR - 2x Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 2620 days / 7.18 years NBR - 2x Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 2720 days / 7.45 years NBR - 2x Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 5005 days / 13.7 years</p> <p>NBR - 2x Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 936 days / 2.56 years</p>

		<p>NBR - 2x Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.01 bar: 966 days / 2.65 years NBR - 2x Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 1785 days / 4.89 years</p> <p>NBR - 2x Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 582 days / 1.59 years NBR - 2x Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 600 days / 1.64 years NBR - 2x Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 1110 days / 3.04 years</p> <p><u>AS 100</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 480 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 495 days / 1.36 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 910 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 1062 days / 2.91 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 170 days NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 176 days / 0,48 years NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 324 days NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 376 days / 1,03 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 106 days / 0,29 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 109 days / 0,30 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 202 days / 0,55 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 242 days / 0,66 years</p> <p><u>HAS 25</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 308 days / 0.84 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 318 days / 0.87 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 588 days / 1.61 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 708 days / 1.94 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 108 days / 0.30 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 112 days / 0,31 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 208 days / 0,57 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 248 days / 0,69 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 68 days / 0,19 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 70 days / 0,19 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 130 days / 0,36 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 156 days / 0,43 years</p>
9	<p>Technical installation blocked between the inlet and outlet valve</p>	<p><u>DS 2500</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 360 days / 1.0 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 369 days / 1.01 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 684 days / 1.9 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 127 days / 0,35 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 132 days / 0,36 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 243 days / 0,67 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 79 days / 0,22 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 82 days / 0,22 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 151 days / 0,41 years</p>

		<p><u>AS 100</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 28 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 29 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 54 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 64 days</p> <p>NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 9.9 days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 10.2 days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 19 days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 22.8 days</p> <p>NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 6.2 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 6.4 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 11.5 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 14 days</p> <p><u>HAS 25</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 24.4 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 25.2 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 46.5 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 55.5 days</p> <p>NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 8.6 days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 8.9 days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 16.5 days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 19.5 days</p> <p>NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 5.4 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 5.5 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 10.24 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 12.32 days</p>
10	Single control line (Spare control line of double control line)	<p><u>DS 2500</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 360 days / 1.0 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 369 days / 1.01 years NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 684 days / 1.9 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 127 days / 0,35 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 132 days / 0,36 years NBR - Ø22,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 243 days / 0,67 years</p> <p>NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,03 bar: 79 days / 0,22 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 0,1 bar: 82 days / 0,22 years NBR - Ø28,00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 151 days / 0,41 years</p> <p><u>AS 100</u> NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 28 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 29 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 54 days NBR - Ø12.25 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 64 days</p> <p>NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 9.9 days</p>

		<p>NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: ... days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 19 days NBR - Ø22.00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 22.8 days</p> <p>NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.03 bar: 6.2 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 0.1 bar: 6.4 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 4 bar: 11.5 days NBR - Ø28.00 cm - 1 mm - 8 bar: 14 days</p>
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